

Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2022

Oct 5, 2022

Assessing Discussions of Related Work through Citation-based Recommendations and Network Visualization

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RELATED WORK

*How can discussions of related work
be reviewed more efficiently?*

Citation-based Recommendations

citation **gecko**

ResearchRabbit

 PURE suggest

 Inciteful

Citation-based literature search

Based on a set of selected publications, **suggesting** related **publications** connected by **references**.

Selected

DOI(s)/title or search

+ Add

Search

To start, **+** **add** publications through a **title** or **DOI(s)**,
🔍 **search** using **keywords**, or:

 Import session from JSON

Suggested

Citation network

Selected

Suggested

Experiment:

- Use a paper that is few years old
- Copy references (with loss)
- Check for lost publications and newer ones

Latif, S., & Beck, F. (2019; first published 2018). VIS Author Profiles: Interactive descriptions of publication records combining text and visualization. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 25(1), 152-161.

Citation network

Selected keyword(s) Boost

DOI(s)/title or search + Add Search

- 3 Method Execution Reports: Generating Text and Visualization to Describe Program Behavior (Beck et al., 2017)
- 3 Word-Sized Graphics for Scientific Texts (Beck and Weiskopf, 2017)
- 2 Exploring the Placement and Design of Word-Scale Visualizations (Goffin et al., 2014)
- 1 Frames and Slants in Titles of Visualizations on Controversial Topics

Suggested 50 of 1,437 Filter

- 7 Explorative Code Quality Documents (Mumtaz et al., 2019)
- 6 Interactive Map Reports Summarizing Bivariate Geographic Data (Latif and Beck, 2019)
- 4 Building Natural Language Generation Systems (Reiter and Dale, 2000) Highly cited
- 3 A Deeper Understanding of Visualization-Text Interplay in Geographic Data-Driven Stories (Latif et al., 2021) New Unnoted

Citation network Mode: Timeline Clusters

Selected generat, visual, text, lang, wc ✕ ⤴ Boost

DOI(s)/title or search + Add 🔍 Search

- 24 ⤴ **Method Execution Reports: Generating Text and Visualization to Describe Program Behavior** (Beck et al., 2017) -
- 24 ⤴ **Word-Sized Graphics for Scientific Texts** (Beck and Weiskopf, 2017) -
- 8 ⤴ **Exploring the Placement and Design of Word-Scale Visualizations** (Goffin et al., 2014) -
- 0 ⤴ **Contextifier: automatic generation of annotated stock visualizations** -

437 ⌵ Filter

2019) + -

raphic Data (Latif + -

and Dale, 2000) + -

y in Geographic + -

Timeline ⬅ Clusters ⌵

Suggested 33 of 1,437 Filter

Search: Text Year: From 2018 Tag: None/any

- 16 Highly cited **Match**

Building Natural Language Generation Systems (Reiter and Dale, 2000)
- 12 **Close match**

Exploring the Effect of Word-Scale Visualizations on Reading Behavior (Goffin et al., 2015)
- 12 Highly cited **Not relevant**

Network Visualization by Semantic Substrates (Shneiderman and Aris, 2006)
- An Exploratory Study of Word-Scale Graphics in Data-Rich Text**

Filter

ata (Latif)

le, 2000)

ographic

Clusters

Suggested

33 of 1,437 Filter

Suggested

6 of 1,437 Filter

Search

Text

Year

2018

To

Tag

Unnoted

12
3

A Deeper Understanding of Visualization-Text Interplay in Geographic Data-Driven Stories (Latif et al., 2021)

New Unnoted

8
2

Automatic Generation of Textual Descriptions in Data-To-Text Systems Using a Fuzzy Temporal Ontology: Application in Air Quality Index Data Series (Cascallar-Fuentes et al., 2022)

New Unnoted

8
2

Visual Analysis of Multilayer Networks (Mcgee et al., 2021)

Literature survey New Unnoted

literatur

How can discussions of related work be reviewed more efficiently?

Citation-based recommendations

- do not replace the expertise of the reviewers
- but help quickly check for missing references

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